

Mechanisms for activating and implementing the innovative potential of the military-industrial complex

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Аннотация. Авторы выявили, систематизировали, изучили и дали оценку организационно-экономическим механизмам, с помощью которых предприятия и корпорации ОПК активизируют свою инновационную деятельность. В статье проанализированы ограничения на рынке сбыта инновационной продукции военного назначения, возникающие из-за конкуренции, санкций, проблем долевого финансирования, ценообразования, а также из-за сложностей взаимодействия с производственным бизнесом и частными военными компаниями. Выявлены трудности экспорта высокотехнологичной продукции оборонно-промышленного комплекса на международные рынки.

Abstract. The authors identified, systematized, studied, and assessed the organizational and economic mechanisms, with the help of which enterprises and corporations of the military-industrial complex enhance its innovative activities. The paper analyzed limitations in the market sale of innovative military products arising due to competition, sanctions, problems of equity financing, pricing, and due to difficulties in interaction with the manufacturing business and private military companies. Difficulties in the export of high-tech products of the military-industrial complex in international markets were identified.

Ключевые слова: инновационная деятельность, военно-промышленный комплекс, продукция военного назначения, госзаказ, частные военные компании, доленое финансирование, производственный бизнес, экспорт.

Keywords: innovative activity, military-industrial complex, military products, government contracts, private military companies, equity financing, manufacturing business, export.

Introduction.

Due to sanctions and complicated modern conditions, a pressing issue will be to develop and implement organizational, financial, and economic mechanisms and methods for improving quality and increasing the real capabilities of corporations and enterprises of the domestic military-industrial complex (MIC) designed to equip the Armed Forces of the Russian Federation with innovative weapons and with military and special equipment (MSE). A successful solution to this problem requires the economic sustainability of the defense industry, as well as the effective use of its scientific, technical, production, technological, financial, and economic potentials to create new (modernized) and competitive defense products [1, 5, 16].

Current and legally approved rules for the creation of defense products using funds from the federal budget and private investors allow stimulating innovative approaches but are not sufficient to solve this issue. To improve and accelerate innovative and proactive creation and production of new types of military equipment, a thorough scientifically based financial and economic assessment of the capabilities of defense corporations and enterprises is required, allowing the development of new mechanisms and methods that will not lead to negative consequences [7, 14].

Limitations in the supply of new types of MSE.

The motivations of defense corporations and enterprises (without taking into account the negative impact of low commercial feasibility) in relation to the proactive proposal of new or modernized models of military equipment are mainly positive, due to the opportunity to increase the serial production to ensure recoupment of the costs incurred for the corresponding innovations and thereby to increase profits. Notably, in recent years due to the worsened foreign economic situation, much similar to the situation at the end of the last century [10, 11], the uncertainty and riskiness of the production, financial, and scientific activities of defense industry enterprises increased.

Currently, defense corporations and enterprises are limited in offering new developments and products in the field of military equipment by the following contractual circumstances:

1. Government contracts included in the state defense order. These contracts usually have a number of negative economic features:

– insignificant volumes of new defense products in terms of cost and quantitative parameters, and, consequently, low financial profit from their sales;

- unsuccessfully organized pricing for corporations and enterprises for new defense products;
- strictly regulated implementation of a state defense contract.

Thus, the recommended option for marketing new types of defense products becomes economically unattractive for corporations and enterprises.

However, despite the listed negatives, corporations and enterprises, to varying degrees, remain interested in concluding such contracts because:

- participation in government contracts guarantees the required financial resources from the federal budget, as well as economic government assistance during global financial crises, for instance, in 2008-2009;

- when implementing the state armament program (SAP), defense corporations and enterprises can participate in the related program for the development of the MIC, which is intended for the technological and scientific-technical modernization of corporations and enterprises of defense products.

2. Export contracts for the sale of military equipment in the global arms market.

Such contracts, as a rule, are economically beneficial for corporations and enterprises exporting their products. Yet fierce international competition in the world market forces manufacturers of military equipment to invest and spend their own funds on increasing production and technological and scientific-technical capabilities, which are then used to create and produce new innovative and competitive weapons and MSE.

However, exporting military equipment often has only local advantages which sometimes do not fully compensate for the costs incurred. At the same time, the export potential of corporations and defense industry enterprises is also decreasing due to the state monopoly on the organization of military-technical interaction between Russia and foreign countries, which limits the ability of domestic manufacturers of military equipment to independently and actively position new military-oriented products in international arms markets.

At the same time, market mechanisms for export require bases of knowledge on military equipment and military sciences and a constant increase in the competitiveness of innovative defense products by the domestic defense industry. To achieve this goal, Russian corporations and enterprises (which lag behind foreign competitors in terms of science, technologies, and production and are under constantly growing sanctions pressure) use the following ineffective methods – price competition by reducing the price of MSE, agreement with financially unfavorable contract terms and conditions and the use of foreign components in export products, which significantly reduces commercial profits and the attractiveness of concluded export contracts.

An analysis of the practices of the global arms market shows that increasing the competitiveness of military equipment is facilitated by their use in the exporting country, which determines the de-

sire of corporations and enterprises to include the models they create in the weapons system of the Russian Armed Forces.

Sales of defense products to private military companies.

This sales area for military equipment emerged in recent years due to the increased activity of private military companies, which are commercial organizations that offer specialized paramilitary services related to defense, protection (sometimes involving participation in major military conflicts), security, as well as strategic planning, consulting, intelligence, and logistics [17]. Such companies appeared because modern transnational corporations (which have significant financial resources) need to protect their interests no less than states.

Modern private military companies, in addition to small arms, may have helicopters, armored personnel carriers, reconnaissance and communications equipment, etc., which makes them active consumers of a wide range of military products. Among these companies, the following stand out:

- providers of direct military services, tactical support, taking part in combat operations (the share of such companies is small);
- consulting services that teach planning, train armed forces, etc.;
- rear, providing logistics, security, evacuation of the wounded, and other needs of the regular army.

Military experts warn that the use of “private military force” in modern armed conflicts is becoming increasingly widespread. In the early 90s, there was one “private owner” for every 50 military personnel; now this ratio is 10:1. For instance, in Afghanistan and Iraq, there are several hundred private military and security companies that are equal subjects of military activity along with the traditional armed forces.

Importantly, when purchasing military products, private military companies are not limited by international laws in the field of arms trade and can purchase them on completely legal (and often illegal) grounds both within the country and abroad.

Positioning of domestic defense corporations and enterprises in the market of military products for private military companies in this period can become an additional way to realize their accumulated reserves [13, 18].

Main motivations for the proactive development of military products.

Notably, the main motivations of corporations and MIC enterprises in promoting the models of military equipment created on their own initiative for the technical equipment of the Russian Armed Forces are:

- striving for the maximum implementation of the accumulated scientific, technical, production, and technological potential as a factor of commercial efficiency [2, 12];
- increasing participation in the technical equipment of the Armed Forces of the Russian Federation, which will ensure commercially not very

profitable but guaranteed sales of a certain part of the products;

- growth in the export potential of military equipment samples due to additional competitive advantages, which arise from these samples being part of the arsenal of the RF Armed Forces;
- moving away from the unprofitable pricing system for defense products and from strict control over the implementation of government defense contracts [6, 9].

Thus, the motivations that subjects of the mechanism for the proactive MSE development have can be multidirectional, which requires the rational role and place of this mechanism in the system of program-target planning for the development of the weapons system of the RF Armed Forces.

Notably, the SAP initially aims to ensure the set of properties of all MSE it includes provides complete coverage of military threats to the Russian Federation. However, in reality, such planning is far from the ideal model, since operational tasks often arise, for example, an operation held to force Georgia to peace, when the weapons system of the Russian Armed Forces turned out to be not fully adequate to the entire range of military threats of that period.

Essentially, this implies the feasibility of forming a mechanism for the proactive development of MSE as an addition to the program-target planning for the development of a weapons system.

Its place in the system of technical equipment of the RF Armed Forces will allow quickly filling the gaps in terms of threats to the military security of the Russian Federation (the SAP did not provide the corresponding types of military equipment to counter these) and, thereby, increasing the efficiency of the technical equipment of the RF Armed Forces.

However, it is necessary to take into account that the widespread practice of proactive development of MSE samples may be associated with potential dangers:

- significant financial losses of government customers in case of terminating work similar to that carried out on an initiative basis (this will have the opposite effect – a decrease in the efficiency of funds allocated for national defense);
- exaggeration of threats to the country's military security (in the interests of creating an appropriate information background for making military-technical decisions necessary for a corporation or enterprise), with all the negative consequences;
- activated mechanisms of unfair lobbying of the interests that corporations and enterprises (as well as investors who proactively developed military equipment) have; as a result, the stability of the technical equipment system of the RF Armed Forces will be disrupted;
- the use (within the framework of MSE initiative development) of components that do not meet the requirements of government customers, since they may not have the opportunity to quickly and in-depth study the created samples due to the

impossibility of timely involvement of military missions [4].

Notably, at present in the technical equipment system of the RF Armed Forces, the task of effectively managing MSE at all stages of their life cycle arises. Therefore, one initiative proposal to include an MSE model developed outside the SAP into the current weapons system is not enough. It is necessary to combine the development trajectory of the model over time with the development trajectory of the weapons system of the RF Armed Forces in the corresponding program period, which is difficult for corporations and MIC enterprises.

Equity financing mechanism.

To a certain extent, the prototype of the mechanism for the MSE proactive development can be a mechanism of equity financing; implementing it creates conditions for introducing commercially significant technologies (implemented by market methods) into creating weapons and MSE by corporations and enterprises [15]. This will provide the opportunity to supplement the federal budget funds allocated for the creation of MSE with private investments in the development of these technologies, with their subsequent use in creating both military and civilian products.

When implementing equity financing, motivations of subjects of the mechanism for proactive creation of MSE are triggered:

- for government customers of military products, primarily the RF Ministry of Defense, a shared financing mechanism will not only reduce the funds spent on creating MSE but also guarantee a certain part of the profit from the sale of products created based on the technologies developed in this case;
- operators will be able, through effective concentration of centralized and decentralized resources in certain areas, to obtain military equipment with higher combat and operational properties;
- for corporations and MIC enterprises, this will intensify innovation activities by combining funds from the federal budget and private investors into a single plan, as well as implementation of the resulting technologies with significant economic benefits.

Conclusion.

The functioning of the mechanism for the proactive development of new (modified) types of weapons and MSE in the proposed version is capable, first, of increasing the efficiency of the technical equipment of the RF Armed Forces without violating the existing system of program-target planning and the balance of the weapons system, and second, of providing corporations and MIC enterprises with channels for implementing their innovations to recoup the costs.

At this stage of such development, it is most advisable to stimulate defense corporations and enterprises to:

- proactive proposal for the development of MSE samples within the framework of the program cycle and mutually beneficial daily cooperation

with private business, ordering and supplying authorities [8];

– search for options for the effective modernization of created MSE models in order to give them new properties that counter unexpected threats to the country's military security;

– development of more advanced components that increase the tactical and technical characteristics of MSE and reduce its cost.

Organizational and economic measures that need to be implemented to transform the initiative development mechanism into an additional factor for increasing the efficiency of technical equipment of the RF Armed Forces should aim at:

– improving the economic conditions for the functioning of the defense industry as a whole and certain categories of its corporations and enterprises (various organizational, legal forms, and forms of ownership) to increase the commercial attractiveness of participating in the state defense order, the status of which should be under strict control;

– improving program-target planning for the development of the weapons system of the RF Armed Forces to make more "entry points" of initiatively created weapons and MSE samples into it, as well as increase its transparency for the real sector of the economy [3];

– resolving issues related to organizing active interaction between all the participants in the initiative development mechanism, primarily ordering authorities, including military missions, defense corporations, and enterprises, as well as involving private businesses;

– developing legal and methodological tools for assessing whether the properties of MSE samples created by defense corporations and enterprises on their own initiative comply with the established requirements;

– creating conditions for enhancing innovative activity in the MIC as a source of innovations necessary for the development of MSE with higher combat and operational qualities.

Bibliography:

1. Batkovsky A.M., Batkovsky M.A., Bozhko V.P., Khrustalev E.Yu. et al. Regulation of the development of basic high-tech industries / edited by A.M. Batkovsky, V.P. Bozhko. – M.: MESI, 2014. – 400 p.

2. Vikulov S.F., Khrustalev E.Yu. Methodology for assessing and improving the effectiveness of the state's defense potential // Polythematic network electronic scientific journal KubGAU. 2015. No. 4. Pp. 533-556.

3. Vikulov S.F., Khrustalev E.Yu. Improving the methodology of program-target planning in the military-financial sphere // National interests: priorities and security. 2015. No. 23. Pp. 2-14.

4. Grigoriev M.N., Sidorov E.A. Procurement activities of defense industry enterprises in conditions of large-scale application of anti-Russian economic sanctions // Logistics systems in the global economy. 2022. No. 12. Pp. 80-83.

5. Lavrinov G.A., Kosenko A.A., Khrustalev E.Yu. The innovative potential of the Russian military-industrial

complex // National interests: priorities and security. Volume 9. No. 22. Pp. 2-14.

6. Lavrinov G.A., Khrustalev E.Yu. Methods of forecasting prices for military products // Forecasting problems. 2006. No. 1. Pp. 87-96.

7. Lavrinov G.A., Khrustalev E.Yu., Khrustalev O.E. Fundamental science as the most important element of the modern system of ensuring military security of the state // Bulletin of the Russian Academy of Sciences. 2017. Volume 87. No. 3. Pp. 195-203.

8. Larin S.N., Khrustalev O.E. Business incubator as an important component of the innovation infrastructure of the region: analysis of foreign and domestic experience // Regional economics: theory and practice. 2009. Volume 7. No. 17. Pp. 27-33.

9. Murnikov I.V. Tax risks manifested through pricing in the defense industry // Accounting, analysis and audit: problems of theory and practice. 2021. No. 27. Pp. 122-126.

10. The Russian economy in 2000. Trends and prospects. Issue 22. – Moscow: Institute for Economic Problems of the Transition Period, 2001. – 375 p.

11. The Russian economy in 2001. Trends and prospects. Issue 23. Vol. 1. – Moscow: Institute for Economic Problems of the Transition Period, 2002. – 620 p.

12. Sinkova Yu.N. The system of indicators of expert assessment of the innovative potential of the defense industry // Economics. Business. Cans. 2020. No. 11. Pp. 32-44.

13. Staursky E.S., Damdinov A.P. The world market of armaments and military equipment: the state and ways of development // Actual problems of law and the state in the XXI century. 2018. Volume 10. No. 4. Pp. 71-76.

14. Khachaturian A.A., Tsalikov Z.R., Laptiev A.I. Directions for the development of financial support for the Armed Forces of the Russian Federation // Economics and entrepreneurship. 2017. No. 3-2. Pp. 132-135.

15. Khrustalev E.Yu., Larin S.N., Khrustalev O.E. Market methods of accelerating the innovative development of high-tech enterprises of the military-industrial complex // Higher school: scientific research. Materials of the Interuniversity International Congress (Moscow, June 9, 2022). – Moscow: Infiniti Publishing House, 2022. Pp. 18-25.

16. Khrustalev O.E. Methodological foundations for assessing the economic sustainability of an industrial enterprise // Audit and financial analysis. 2011. No. 5. Pp. 180-185.

17. Zhocho Yu., Grozin A.V. Private military companies: reasons for their appearance, main features and legal status // Post-Soviet mainland. 2022. No. 4. Pp. 16-28.

18. Shaburova P.A. Analysis of the competitive environment in the promotion of armaments and military equipment (VIV) on the world market // Power of systems. 2020. No. 3. Pp. 66-73.